

TECHNIQUES OF CONTENT ORGANIZATION FOR A GOOD LECTURE

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Introduction

Lecture is probably the oldest teaching method and still the method is widely used in Indian colleges and universities. Effective lecture combine the talents of a scholar , writer , producer and teacher in ways that contribute to student learning.

The use of lecturing depends upon the subject matter, the teaching philosophy of the instructor and the overall learning situation. Appropriate lectures can build structures and expectations that help students read material in the given subject matter area more effectively.

As you know, every discipline has its own structure that organizes its content. Hence, topics in different disciplines may demand different ways of organization of a lecture.

Content organization – some parameters:-

A teacher cannot choose his style of content treatment arbitrarily. He has to keep in his mind a number of parameters. These may include learner's ability, interest and the psychological sequencing. There are mainly three kinds of psychological sequencing the teacher can refer to, while deciding a particular style of treating the content.

These are:-

- a) Familiar to unfamiliar
- b) Simple to complex
- c) Ensuring success experience – rewarding

There are some specific technique which a teacher can make use of while organizing the content matter and activities to be undertaken in the classroom.

- i) **Flowchart:-** It is possible to prepare a flowchart of the teaching points in your topics and the task/ activities you plan to give to your students. This technique can be used for lesson planning. It is also used to prepare a summary of the topic which can be shared with students study the following example of a flowchart and prepare similar flowchart for one of your lecture selecting a topic from discipline that you are teaching.

*** Flow chart of function of lecture**

I) Planning before the lecture

- ii) **Matrices:-** You can prepare matrices of the teaching points of your topics. Matrices are two dimensional charts which show the relationship among the concepts, ideas, events, principles etc. on two dimensions.
- iii) **Content mapping:-** This as a technique which you may use to organize your content. Beginning with the central topic or concept or skill or job, you write down all the related ideas, flowing down from your central idea.

e.g.

iv) Progressive display of content structure:-

Content can be organized and conveyed very effectively by presenting them in stages, progressively building up the whole structure as you explain it's component, but explaining the content structure (verbally as in written form) may not be meaningful. Instead, diagrams and visual presentations often work better than the spoken or written word in portraying structures. There are different ways of displaying this structuring one can use an overhead projector (OHP) transparency to display the structure as it develops. Another way of progressive building of structures can be by writing elements into bare framework. This framework may be given to students in a handout for them to complete. It can be done in the following way.

Framework for progressive structure

Such progressive building of structure is valuable when:-

- a) The structure is rather complex to take in all at once.
- b) The way the structure develops and the way its components are related need to be shown.
- c) Changes overtime (in historical developments, the elaboration of a theory, the development of machine etc.) are important.

Conclusion:

Poor choice of subject or lack of sufficient knowledge about it may mean death for a lecture.

Good lectures probably do intuitively many of the things suggested above . Becoming conscious of what is going on in students head as we talk , being alert to feedback from students through their facial expressions , non-verbal behavior or oral comments adjusting one's strategies in reference to these clues , these will help the lecturer learn and help students to learn from the lecturer more effectively.

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